

± 0.3%. Serious interference was observed only with iron(III), thorium(IV), titanium(IV), vanadium(V) and lanthanum(III). Similarly fluoride added as a sodium salt also caused interference. Tantalum, niobium and tungsten are not usually present in chloride solution. Other elements have not been investigated but they rarely occur in association with zirconium.

Application to zircon—Well powdered zircon was converted to zirconium oxychloride^{1,2} taking care to remove all interfering ions. A stock solution was then prepared and a suitable aliquot was estimated using N-acetylacetone anthranilic acid. The results thus obtained compared favourably with those given by mandelic acid method.

The analysis of the dark-brown chelate displayed the metal ligand ratio to be 1 : 1.

Found ZrO₂, 34.8 ; C, 41.3 ; H, 4.51 ; N, 4.32%
Calc ZrO₂, 35.99 ; C, 42.08 ; H, 3.79 ; N, 4.09%

The infrared spectra of the zirconium chelate indicated the absence of characteristic absorptions for -OH and -COOH groups. However the strong absorption of the ligand at 1650 cm⁻¹ due to νC=O is shifted to lower frequencies in the chelate and appears at 1600 cm⁻¹. A strong band at 1550 cm⁻¹ due to νC=N is shifted to 1500 cm⁻¹ in the complex. These shifts towards lower frequencies show that C=N and C=O are involved in bond formation. The absence of a band around 1100-800 cm⁻¹ due to ν Zr=O^{1,3-15} rule out the possibility of Zr=O bond in the chelate.

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Bi-ionic Potentials of Uni-bi Anionic System with 'Neosepta' Membranes

S. K. SAHARAY and A. S. BASU

Department of Chemistry, The University of Burdwan, Burdwan-713 104, West Bengal, India

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BI-IONIC potentials are complex phenomena and the studies become more complex if the counter-ions are of different valencies due to the unknown parameters like the membrane phase activities and the mobilities of the ions within the membrane. However, several attempts were made by various workers¹⁻³ to study the uni-bi systems for different purposes.

In this short communication the multi-ionic potential equation of Wyllie⁴ is rearranged to a simpler form in case of bi-ionic potential of uni-bi anionic system with two assumptions.

(i) For a high capacity ion-exchanger membrane, the activities of the ions within the membrane may be assumed to be constant over the range of Nernstian response, and

(ii) the intra-membrane mobilities remain constant over the range of permselectivity of the membrane.

The rearranged equation for uni-bi anionic system takes the form as

$$E_{BTP} = -\frac{2.303RT}{2F} \log a_B + \frac{2.303RT}{F} \log a_M + C \dots (1)$$

where C, a constant, is given by

$$C = -\frac{2.303RT}{2F} \log \frac{\bar{a}_M^2}{\bar{a}_B} - \frac{2.303RT}{F} \left[\frac{\bar{a}_B \bar{U}_B - \bar{a}_M \bar{U}_M}{2\bar{a}_B \bar{U}_B - \bar{a}_M \bar{U}_M} \right] \log \frac{2\bar{a}_B \bar{U}_B}{\bar{a}_M \bar{U}_M} \dots (2)$$

\bar{a}_B , \bar{a}_M are the membrane phase activities and \bar{U}_B , \bar{U}_M are the intra-membrane mobilities of the bivalent (B⁻²) and monovalent (M⁻) anions respectively.

The equation (1) has been applied for verification in case of $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{Cl}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{Br}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{I}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{NO}_3^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{BrO}_3^-$ and $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{IO}_3^-$ pairs with the three anion exchanger 'Neosepta' membranes AV-3, AV-3T and AVS-3T.

The preparations of the electrodes and the electrolytic solutions were done in the usual procedure⁶. The membrane potentials are measured with the conventional set up the bi-ionic cell^{6,7}. The validity of equation (1) is tested by two techniques of measurements (i) method of Wyllie^{7,8} and (ii) method of Sollner^{7,9}. B.I.P.s are recorded from a higher to a lower concentration but within the range of Nernstian response¹⁰.

In the Wyllie method the two sets of B. I.P. values are plotted graphically and the magnitudes of 'C' are calculated using equation (1) from the evaluated slope values of the graphs. In the Sollner method $a_x = a_y = a$ (say) and the equation (1) takes the form as

$$E = \frac{2.303RT}{2F} \log a + C \quad \dots (3)$$

where C is given by the expression (2). The 'C' values are calculated from equation (3) using the experimental slope value for each B.I.P. value and average is taken. Regarding the sign of e.m.f. the usual sign convention^{9,11} is followed.

Excellent straight lines obtained in both the methods of measurements qualitatively justify the assumptions involved in the rearrangement of Wyllie's equation of uni-bi system. But from the quantitative view point the differences are observed between the two methods of measurement with respect to the evaluated parameters. In the Wyllie method the graphical slope values show slight deviations from the theoretical values of 29.5 mv for the bivalent and 59.1 mv for the monovalent variable lines at 25° for all the systems with the three membranes. However, considering the various implied assumptions in these measurements of B.I.P.s viz. (i) Non-thermodynamic assumptions of single ion activity, (ii) assumption of constant activity within the membrane and (iii) assumption of the complete membrane diffusion control, which may not be real particularly in case of BIP of unequal valency, the agreement on the slope values may be said to be quite fair.

The most probable explanation for this deviation is that, due to the wide difference of water activities on both sides, possibly the secondary phenomenon of water transport takes place which is evident in view of earlier studies¹⁰. The interesting point is that the greater the hydrated ionic size, the greater is the deviation in the slope values e.g. with AVS-3T membrane for the pairs $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{NO}_3^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{BrO}_3^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{IO}_3^-$ the slope values of univalent variable

lines are 54.7, 52.1, 52.0 respectively whereas the hydrated ionic volumes of the ions follow an increasing order as $\text{NO}_3^- (94.92) < \text{BrO}_3^- (109.2) < \text{IO}_3^- (132.1)$. But when the hydrated ionic volumes of the univalent ions do not differ widely the slopes are also not much different from each other. viz. with AV-3 membrane for the pairs $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{Cl}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{I}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{Br}^-$ the slope values of univalent variable lines are 54.4, 54.2, 56.8 respectively whereas the hydrated ionic values of the ions follow the order as $\text{Cl}^- (92.39) > \text{I}^- (91.56) > \text{Br}^- (90.73)$. However, if there are any other factors influencing the slope value is not clear at this stage.

In the method of Sollner where the activities of the two ions are the same on the two sides the slope values are not affected to such an extent, e.g., with AVS-3T membrane for the pairs $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{Cl}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{Br}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{I}^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{NO}_3^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{BrO}_3^-$, $\text{SO}_4^{2-}-\text{IO}_3^-$ the slope values are 28.2, 28.5, 28.5, 28.5, 28.0, 28.0 respectively. Similar is the result with other pairs and with other membranes. Here the straight lines obtained are in conformity with equation (3) and the slope values are quite good as has been anticipated.

The values of the constant 'C' are calculated from the equation (1) for different membranes in different systems. For a particular pair of ions the magnitudes of the constant are not equal in the different membranes studied. However, it is observed that for a particular pair if the slope values are not widely different for different membranes, the magnitudes of 'C' are also not far from each other.

The behaviour of AVS-3T membrane is quite different from the other two membranes. The greater preference of AVS-3T membrane for the univalent anions can be visualised from the sign and the magnitudes of the e.m.f. values particularly with sulphate-halide pairs. Moreover, the affinity for the halide ions over that of the sulphate ion follows the order, $\text{I}^- > \text{Br}^- > \text{Cl}^-$ which is in agreement with the earlier observations⁷.

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Constituents of *Aspergillus niger*

H. K. BHAT, G. N. QAZI, C. L. CHOPRA, K. L. DHAR*
and
C. K. ATAL

Regional Research Laboratory, Jammu Tawi-180 001

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ASPERGILLUS niger is a fungus commonly used in the commercial production of citric acid. The wet mycelium is obtained in large quantities after the recovery of citric acid. Since this mycelial mat, 1 kg dry wt. obtained for every 10 kg of citric acid produced, is at present going waste, it was thought worthwhile to study its chemical composition, with the objective of finding some useful byproducts.

The dried ground mycelium (4 kg) was extracted with light petroleum (b.p. 60-80°) in a soxhlet for 42 hrs. Chromatography of the extract over silica gel and rechromatography over alumina yielded three distinct fractions. Fraction "1" contained stearic acid, m.p. 70-71°, identified from spectroscopic data and formation of derivatives.

Fraction "2" yielded on crystallisation from methanol-benzene shining crystals, (0.3 g), m.p. 145-146°, showing positive test for sterols. Analytical data suggested its molecular formula to be $C_{28}H_{44}O$, confirmed by mass spectrum which showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 396, the other prominent peaks being at m/e 363, 337 and 271. Pmr⁺ showed signals at δ 0.64-1.16 (six methyls), 3.5 (1H, D₂O exchangeable, C3-OH), 5.22 (2H, broad multiplet, C22, 23-olefinic protons) and 5.5 (1H, multiplet, C15-H).

It gave a monoacetate, $C_{30}H_{46}O_2$, m.p. 148-149°, [α]_D -60° (CHCl₃), ν_{max}^{nujol} 1240 cm⁻¹ (Acetate). Pmr showed a singlet at δ 2.01 (3H, -OCOCH₃). Oxidation

† All PMR spectra in this paper were measured in CCl₄ solution with TMS as internal standard in a 60 MHz instrument.

(Jones)⁸ of the sterol formed a 3-keto compound, m.p. 162°, ν_{max}^{nujol} 1717 cm⁻¹ (C=O stretching). On hydrogenation (Pd/C, 5%) the sterol absorbed 2 moles of hydrogen forming the tetrahydro derivative, m.p. 152°, which when further subjected to hydrogenation (Pd/C, acetic acid) absorbed one more mole of hydrogen to yield the hexahydro derivative, thus showing that there are three double bonds and that one of the double bonds is tetra substituted.

The above physico-chemical evidences suggested the compound to be 24-methyl-5 β -cholesta-8, 14, 22-trien-3 β -ol(I) (lit⁹, m.p. 144-5°), confirmed by m.m.p. and co-tlc with an authentic sample.

Fraction "3" furnished a white crystalline solid (0.2 g) m.p. 178°. It also showed positive test for sterols. Analytical data suggested its molecular formula to be $C_{28}H_{44}O_3$, confirmed by mass spectrometry which showed a molecular ion peak at m/e 428, the other peaks being at 410, 396, 392 and 376 mass units. Pmr shows signals at δ 6.38 (2H, AB quartet, J=6Hz, 6H & 7-H), 5.25 (2H, broad multiplet, 22-H & 23-H), 3.9 (1H, D₂O exchangeable, 3-OH) and 0.93 to 1.4 (six methyls).

The above data indicated its identity with ergosterol peroxide(II)^{11,14}, confirmed by comparison (m.m.p., co-tlc) with an authentic sample and by the formation of its acetate, m.p. 202-203°, [α]_D -23° (CHCl₃).

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